

A semi-parametric model for small area estimation using support vector machine

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Abstract

The Fay-Herriot model (Fay & Herriot, 1979) is frequently used in small area estimation (SAE). The Fay-Herriot model assumes a linear relationship between the response and predictor variables, which in practice may not be appropriate. In this research, we extend the Fay-Herriot model to a more general semi-parametric model for small area estimation (SP-SAE), in which the nonparametric component is estimated by machine learning tools such as support vector machine. A back fitting algorithm is proposed to solve the SP-SAE problem. An example using American Community Survey (ACS) data shows that the proposed SP-SAE model significantly improved the health insurance coverage estimates by reducing the bias and variance simultaneously, compared with the Fay-Herriot model.

Key Words: American Community Survey, area-level model, backfitting, semi-parametric model, small area estimation

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily represent the official position of the National Center for Health Statistics, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

1 Introduction

A small area typically refers to a sub-population or domain of interest for which a reliable estimate, based on the domain-specific sample, cannot be produced due to small sample sizes in the domain. Besides the direct domain estimation, small area estimation (SAE) consists of

three main approaches: (1) traditional linear mixed models such as Fay and Herriot (1979), Battese, Harter, and Fuller (1988) and Jiang and Lahiri (2001); (2) nonparametric methods such as Opsomer, Claeskens, Ranalli, Kauermann, and Breidt (2008), Ugarte, Goicoa, Mil- itino, and Durbán (2009) and Salvati, Chandra, Giovanna Ranalli, and Chambers (2010); and (3) Bayesian approaches such as Manton et al. (1989), Rao (1999), and Rao and Molina (2015, chapters 9 and 10). Jiang and Rao (2020) provides a comprehensive review of SAE methods.

When the relationship between the response and the predictors is nonlinear, nonpara- metric regression methods can be applied in small area estimation. Opsomer et al. (2008) combines a penalized spline (p-spline) fit and random area effects. Due to computational issues, their proposed estimator only includes a single predictor variable. Support vector regression (SVR) (Vapnik, 1991) is a supervised nonparametric tool for regression problems. SVR uses an ϵ -insensitive loss function to penalize data points when they are greater than ϵ (Vapnik, 1995). Similar to ridge regression, cubic smoothing splines, thin plate splines and other regularization approaches, SVR also employs general concepts of the theory of reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces (Wahba, 1990). One of the advantages of SVR is that it can handle multiple regression efficiently while using decreased computational resources from the system.

This research extends the Fay-Herriot model to a more general semi-parametric model for small area estimation (SP-SAE), in which the nonparametric component is estimated by SVR. A procedure utilizing multiple random splits (Zhang & He, 2022(a)), binomial tests, and paired t-tests is used to compare the linear and nonlinear models. The general information criterion suggested by Zhang and Pleis (2022(b)) is used to select important variables for regression analysis.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we review a general procedure for model comparisons and the Fay-Herriot model; In Section 3, we propose the SP-SAE and a back fitting algorithm to derive the estimators. In Section 4, we apply the proposed methods to the county-level American Community Survey (ACS) data to estimate health insurance coverage. Finally Section 5 gives some concluding remarks.

2 Background

This section reviews an evaluation procedure for model comparisons (Zhang & He, 2022(a)) using binomial tests and paired t-tests, and reviews the Fay-Herriot model for small area

estimation.

2.1 A general algorithm for model comparisons

The main idea of the algorithm is to randomly choose multiple data splits, therefore creating multiple training sets and test sets. Suppose we are interested in comparing r models. The proposed Monte Carlo simulation algorithm for multiple splits is as follows:

Algorithm 1: General Monte Carlo simulation procedure

Randomly create K splits and save the splits to K different files

for *each split* **do**

 read the split from the data file;

for *each model* $(1, 2, \dots, r)$ **do**

 fit the model with the training data;

 use the fitted model to predict the test data;

 compute the measures of prediction performance;

 record the results to the output file;

Use statistical tools (binomial and paired t-tests) to analyze the results in the output file;

Algorithm 1 can be carried out by parallel computing. We can, for example, request $K/10$ processors and let each processor do the computations for 10 splits simultaneously. For each of the splits, suppose $s\%$ of the randomly selected observations (rounded to the nearest integer) are in the training set, and the rest are in the test set. To measure prediction precision, define prediction error (PE) for the k th test set as

$$PE_k = \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{test set } k} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n * (1 - s\%)},$$

where \hat{y}_i is the fitted value from the regression models, n is the sample size, and $n * (1 - s\%)$ is the size of the test set.

Another commonly used measure of prediction quality is the explained variance (EV) that is defined as the proportion of the variance that is explained by the model. Let $\bar{y}_k = \sum_{i \in \text{test set } k} y_i / (n * (1 - s\%))$ and $\text{Var}(y_k) = \sum_{i \in \text{test set } k} (y_i - \bar{y}_k)^2 / (n * (1 - s\%))$ be the sample mean and variance of the k th test set, respectively. EV for the k th test set is defined as

$$EV_k = 1 - \frac{PE_k}{\text{Var}(y_k)}.$$

EV compares a suggested model to the simplest model using mean prediction for the response y (mean model). If $\hat{y}_i = \bar{y}_k$, PE_k is equal to $\text{Var}(y_k)$, so that $EV_k = 0\%$. Any improvement in

prediction performance will lead to a decrease in PE_k , thus increasing EV up to its possible maximum value of 100%.

2.2 Hypothesis testing

Algorithm 1 creates an output file with PEs related to the K splits. This section reviews the binomial tests and paired t-tests using the output file from Algorithm 1 for comparisons of the r models. Let y_i be the response, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ be the vector of parameters, $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{id})$ be the covariates, and $f(\mathbf{x}_i)$ be a smooth function. Suppose we are interested in the following two models,

$$y_i = \mathbf{x}_i' \boldsymbol{\beta} + \epsilon_i \quad (1)$$

and

$$y_i = f(\mathbf{x}_i) + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where $\epsilon_i \stackrel{iid}{\sim} N(0, \sigma^2)$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Model (1) is a linear model and model (2) is a nonparametric regression model.

2.2.1 Binomial test

For split 1, use the training set to build models (1) and (2); next use the test set to calculate the PEs. Repeat the procedure for the K splits, and compare the proportion where the PE of model (1) is smaller than that of model (2) to 1/2. This is equivalent to testing

$$H_0 : p \geq 1/2 \text{ versus } H_\alpha : p < 1/2, \quad (3)$$

where p is the proportion of all possible splits with the PE of model (1) smaller than that of model (2). Let L be the number of all possible splits in the population. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, L$, define

$$r_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{PE of model (1) is smaller than that of model (2) for split } i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We have $p = \sum_{i=1}^L r_i / L$. Hypothesis (3) is equivalent to

$$H_0 : p = 1/2 \text{ versus } H_\alpha : p < 1/2. \quad (4)$$

Reject H_0 when $R < R_\alpha^*$, where R is the number of random splits where model (1) has a smaller PE and R_α^* can be found from the cumulative distribution function of the binomial distribution. For example, randomly split the data 100 times, i.e., $K = 100$. At the level of

$\alpha = 0.05$, reject H_0 when $R < R_\alpha^* = 42$. The confidence interval of p can be constructed by the normal approximation for the binomial distributions. For example, if $\hat{p} = \frac{R}{K} = 0.8$, then the margin of error is $z_{\alpha/2} * \sqrt{0.8 * (1 - 0.8)/100}$ and a 95% confidence interval can be found as $[0.7216, 0.8784]$. We may increase the number of random splits K to reduce the margin of error.

2.2.2 Paired t-test

Another test is to compare the PEs using a paired t -test. Let $PE_i^{(1)}$ and $PE_i^{(2)}$ be the prediction error from model (1) and model (2) for the i th test set, respectively. Define the PE improvement as

$$\delta_i = PE_i^{(1)} - PE_i^{(2)}. \quad (5)$$

Reject H_0 if the confidence interval for the true PE improvement $D = E(\delta_i)$ is positive. An estimator of D is as follows,

$$\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \delta_i. \quad (6)$$

The sample variance of δ_i is,

$$s^2(\delta_i) = \frac{L - K}{L - 1} * \frac{1}{K - 1} \sum_{i=1}^K (\delta_i - \bar{\delta})^2. \quad (7)$$

A two-sided confidence interval for D is as follows:

$$\left[\bar{\delta} - t_{1-\alpha/2, K-1} * \sqrt{\frac{s^2(\delta_i)}{K}}, \bar{\delta} + t_{1-\alpha/2, K-1} * \sqrt{\frac{s^2(\delta_i)}{K}} \right], \quad (8)$$

where $t_{1-\alpha/2, K-1}$ is the critical value from the t distribution with significance level of α and with $K - 1$ degrees of freedom.

2.3 Fay-Herriot model for SAE

Suppose that the direct small area estimates and area-level auxiliary data are available. Consider m areas $i = 1, \dots, m$. Let \bar{Y}_i be the population area mean, and \bar{y}_i be the sample area mean, which is the direct estimator of \bar{Y}_i . A commonly used model for SAE is the area-level Fay-Herriot model (Fay & Herriot, 1979):

sampling model: $\bar{y}_i = \bar{Y}_i + e_i, \quad e_i \sim N(0, \psi_i)$,

linking model: $\bar{Y}_i = \mathbf{z}_i' \boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i$, where \mathbf{z}_i are covariates, and $v_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$,

and the combined model:

$$\bar{y}_i = \mathbf{z}_i' \boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i + e_i. \quad (9)$$

The empirical best (EB) estimator (Rao, 2003) is as follows:

$$\hat{y}_i^{EB1} = \hat{\gamma}_i \bar{y}_i + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i) \mathbf{z}'_i \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS} \quad (10)$$

Where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}$ is the generalized least square estimator for $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_v^2 / (\hat{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$.

3 Proposed Semi-parametric Small Area Estimator (SP-SAE)

One problem of the Fay-Herriot model is the possible misspecification of the linear linking function, which in practice may not be applicable. To relax the linear assumption, we propose a semi-parametric area-level model for SAE utilizing SVR (SP-SAE). Let's begin with a nonparametric area-level model.

Sampling model $\bar{y}_i = \bar{Y}_i + e_i$, $e_i \sim N(0, \psi_i)$ where ψ_i is known.

Linking model: $\bar{Y}_i = f(\mathbf{z}_i) + v_i$, where \mathbf{z}_i are covariates, $f(\mathbf{z}_i)$ is a smooth function, and $v_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$.

Combined model:

$$\bar{y}_i = f(\mathbf{z}_i) + v_i + e_i \quad (11)$$

The EB estimator can be derived as

$$\hat{y}_i^{EB2} = \hat{\gamma}_i \bar{y}_i + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i) \hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_i),$$

where $\hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_i)$ is estimated by SVR and $\hat{\gamma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_v^2 / (\hat{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$. A more general semi-parametric area-level model (SP-SAE) can be formulated as follows:

Sampling model $\bar{y}_i = \bar{Y}_i + e_i$, $e_i \sim N(0, \psi_i)$ where ψ_i is known.

Linking model: $\bar{Y}_i = \mathbf{z}'_{ai} \boldsymbol{\beta} + f(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) + v_i$, where \mathbf{z}_{ai} and \mathbf{z}_{bi} are subsets of \mathbf{z}_i , $f(\mathbf{z}_{bi})$ is a smooth function, and $v_i \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$.

Combined model:

$$\bar{y}_i = \mathbf{z}'_{ai} \boldsymbol{\beta} + f(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) + v_i + e_i. \quad (12)$$

The EB estimator can be derived as

$$\hat{y}_i^{EB3} = \hat{\gamma}_i \bar{y}_i + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i)(\mathbf{z}'_{ai} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} + \hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_{bi})) \quad (13)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$ is estimated by likelihood-based methods such as maximum likelihood (ML) or restricted maximum likelihood (REML), $\hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_{bi})$ is estimated by SVR, and $\hat{\gamma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_v^2 / (\hat{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$. Note that when $f \equiv 0$, the SP-SAE reduces to the Fay-Herriot model; and when $\boldsymbol{\beta} = 0$, SP-SAE reduces to the nonparametric model.

Next we propose a back-fitting EB estimator for model (12). The back-fitting (BF) idea (Buja, Hastie, & Tibshirani, 1989) is popular for additive models and is easy to understand and implement. Opsomer and Ruppert (1997) provided a strong convergence condition for bivariate additive models and theoretically proved that the BF algorithm was efficient. Later, Xia (2009) provided a weaker condition which guarantees the convergence of the BF algorithm when kernel smoothing is used.

The proposed BF algorithm for SP-SAE is as follows:

$$\hat{y}_i^{EB4} = \hat{\gamma}_i^* \bar{y}_i + (1 - \hat{\gamma}_i^*)(\mathbf{z}'_{ai} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}^* + \hat{f}^*(\mathbf{z}_{bi})) \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{\gamma}_i^* = \tilde{\sigma}_v^2 / (\tilde{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}^*$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$ are the estimates derived by Algorithm 2 (see below). First, fit model (9) and get EB estimator (10); next use the residual $\bar{y}_i - \hat{y}_i^{EB1}$ as the response and fit model (11) to estimate $\hat{f}^*(\mathbf{z}_{bi})$; update the residual as $\bar{y}_i - \hat{f}^*(\mathbf{z}_{bi})$ and repeat the above two steps until convergence. Algorithm 2 gives detailed steps to derive the estimators (similar to Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2001)).

Algorithm 2: back fitting the SP-SAE

Set $\mathbf{z}_i = \mathbf{z}_{ai}$ and fit model (9) and get EB estimator (10) with $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$ and $\hat{\gamma}_i = \hat{\sigma}_v^2 / (\hat{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$;

repeat

fit the residual as the response in model (11), $\bar{y}_i - \mathbf{z}'_{ai} \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS} = f(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) + v_i + e_i$
 where \hat{f} is estimated by SVR;

fit the residual as the response in model (9), $\bar{y}_i - \hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) = \mathbf{z}'_{ai} \boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i + e_i$ where
 $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{GLS}$ and σ_v^2 are estimated as $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$;

until $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$ converge. Let $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{GLS}^*$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$ be the converged estimates.;

$\hat{f}^*(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) = \hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_{bi})$ and $\hat{\gamma}_i^* = \tilde{\sigma}_v^2 / (\tilde{\sigma}_v^2 + \psi_i)$.

Note that $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$ from the back fitting method is different from $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$. To derive the estimator $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$, we use equation (12),

$$\bar{y}_i - \mathbf{z}'_{ai} \boldsymbol{\beta} - f(\mathbf{z}_{bi}) = v_i + e_i.$$

For the i th area,

$$\text{Var}(\bar{y}_i - \mathbf{z}'_{ai}\boldsymbol{\beta} - f(\mathbf{z}_{bi})) = \sigma_v^2 + \psi_i.$$

A method of moment type estimator (MoM) for σ_v^2 can be derived as follows,

$$\hat{\sigma}_v^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \max[(\bar{y}_i - \mathbf{z}'_{ai}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \hat{f}(\mathbf{z}_{bi}))^2 - \psi_i], 0]}{m}. \quad (15)$$

4 Applications

The data was downloaded from the Census Bureau via the Application Programming Interface (API) (<https://www.census.gov/data/developers/data-sets.html>). All the computing was performed in R hosted on a federated high-performance computing cluster at the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

4.1 Data exploration

The American Community Survey (ACS) (<https://www.census.gov/programs-surveys/acs>) is a complex sample survey with information on topics such as demographics, income, employment, occupation, housing, health insurance, education, and veteran status. Figure 1 shows the direct estimate for current health insurance coverage for the 3142 counties in the United States from 2011-2015. The interest of this study is to use SP-SAE to potentially improve the health insurance coverage estimates based on the 2011-2015 ACS data. Nineteen predictors such as demographics, income, and education are considered in the regression analysis (refer to Appendix for further details regarding the variables used).

To see which variables are important in modeling, we applied the general information criterion (GIC) (Zhang & Pleis, 2022(b)) for variable selection. The inclusion frequencies of 10 variables AGERATIO, HOMEVALUE, HouINCOME, PCE, POB, POH, POVERTY, SECURITY, STATE, and UNEMPLOY are all 100%. The inclusion frequencies of variables CHILDREN and FEMALEH are both 97%, followed by COMMUTE30 as 3% and PHS as 1%. Therefore, the 12 variables with inclusion frequencies of at least 97% were selected for regression modeling (reduced model). We compared the linear model with all the 19 variables (full model), the linear reduced model and the nonparametric regression model using SVR with the 12 variables by using binomial and paired t-tests based on Algorithm 1 (Zhang & He, 2022(a)).

For a split ratio of 80% (training set size), we randomly selected 80% of the counties in each state for training and the rest of the counties in the testing set for each split. All

Health Insurance Coverage by county during 2011~2015
 American Community Survey Estimates

Figure 1: Health Insurance Coverage

	Number of times (out of 100 splits) when PE (column) < PE (row)		
	Full model	Reduced model	Nonlinear SVR
Full model	X	75	100
Reduced model	X	X	99
SVR	X	X	X
	PE improvements δ (SE) (Paired t-tests)		
Full model	X	0.0616(0.0785)	1.8050(0.6373)
Reduced model	X	X	1.7434(0.6369)
SVR	X	X	X

Table 1: Binomial and paired t-tests with split ratio of 80%

possible splits are equally likely to be selected and they have the same sizes for training and testing. The upper panel of Table 1 presents the number of times where a model (column) had a smaller PE than the reference model (row) for the binomial test. For a 95% confidence level, counts greater than 58 provide evidence that one model (column) has a lower PE than the other (row). The nonparametric regression model with SVR does outperform the full model and the reduced model. The lower panel of Table 1 also presents the mean (equation 6) and standard error (SE) of the prediction error improvements δ_i . It can be shown that the margin of errors $z_{\alpha/2} * SE * \sqrt{1/100}$ are all smaller than the means. Therefore, all paired t -tests are significant since confidence intervals do not include zero. This indicates that nonlinear SVR performs significantly better than the full model and reduced model, and the reduced model performs significantly better than the full model. We conclude that the nonparametric form is appropriate to model the mean function.

The average of the explained variances from SVR and the reduced linear model are 74.81% and 68.92%, respectively. This means that 5.88% more variation in health insurance coverage from the test set is explained by the nonlinear SVR, compared to the reduced linear model.

4.2 Results

Data exploration shows that the nonparametric regression model is appropriate for the 2011-2015 ACS data. Hence we use SP-SAE to potentially improve health insurance coverage estimates by reducing the bias and variance simultaneously. We set the categorical variable “STATE” as a linear component and all other 11 continuous variables as non-parametric components. The SP-SAE model (12) was fit using Algorithm 2 for 12 iterations. The iterative algorithm was stopped based on tolerance criteria. Results are reported in Table 2, where $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$ is estimated from the BF algorithm and $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$ is estimated by MoM (equation (15)) for each iteration. Figure 2 plots the variance estimates versus iteration, where the red line is for BF fitting and blue line is for MoM fitting. We can see that both estimators converge very quickly starting at the second iteration. $\hat{\sigma}_v^2$ converges to 4.85 (approx.) and $\tilde{\sigma}_v^2$ converges to 2.96 (approx.).

Figure 2: Variance estimate versus iteration, red=BF, blue=MoM

Iteration	$\hat{\sigma}_v^2(\text{BF})$	$\hat{\sigma}_v^2(\text{MoM})$
1	11.1171	13.1370
2	3.5690	5.3887
3	3.2599	5.0989
4	3.1237	4.9730
5	3.0648	4.9267
6	3.0227	4.9031
7	3.0079	4.8962
8	2.9881	4.8765
9	2.9802	4.8683
10	2.9730	4.8603
11	2.9660	4.8546
12	2.9635	4.8532

Table 2: Variance estimation

For comparison purposes, we fit the classical area-level Fay-Herriot model (9) and obtain $\hat{\sigma}_v^2 = 5.42$ (approx.) [not shown]. Compared to the Fay-Herriot model, the SP-SAE MoM estimator achieves about 10.51% variance reduction, and the SP-SAE BF estimator achieves about 45.4% variance reduction and with larger predictive power. This means that the between-area variation becomes smaller when a nonparametric component $f(\cdot)$ is added to the Fay-Herriot model, so that the shrinkage component $(1 - \hat{\gamma}_i)$ becomes larger, which means small areas can borrow more strength from the other areas. In other words, for this example, the SP-SAE model is preferred over the Fay-Herriot model.

The coefficient of variation (CV) is the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean and shows the extent of variability in relation to the mean of the population (Lohr, 2021, page 42). The higher the CV, the greater the dispersion. From Figure 3(a), we can see that the CV of the Fay-Herriot estimator (FH:blue) is significantly smaller than that of the direct estimator (Direct:red). Notice that there are three obvious outliers (CV above 10) for the direct estimates, which are Kenedy county and Loving county from Texas and Clark county from Idaho. From the same source (ACS 2015), the population of these three counties are only 565, 117 and 901, respectively. Compared to the first quartile of the county population size of 11030, these three counties are identified as small areas. Direct estimates for these small areas have large CVs, therefore producing inaccurate estimates. While the Fay-Herriot estimator smoothed these outliers and improved the health insurance coverage

(a) CV by county, red: direct estimator, blue: FH estimator

(b) CV by county, red: FH, blue: SP-SAE

Figure 3: Coefficient of Variance (CV) by County

estimates, figure 3(b) shows that the proposed SP-SAE (blue) outperforms the Fay-Herriot estimator (red).

5 Conclusion

The Fay-Herriot model uses a linear linking function, which may not be appropriate when the relationship is nonlinear. This research extends the linear linking function to a semi-parametric function for small area estimation (SP-SAE), which considers the Fay-Herriot model as a special case. This research also proposed a back-fitting algorithm to solve the SP-SAE problem. An example using health insurance coverage estimates from the 2011-2015 ACS shows that the prediction errors from the linear model are significantly larger than the nonparametric regression model. The estimate of σ_v^2 from the Fay-Herriot model is also larger than that from the SP-SAE, which indicates that the between-area variation becomes smaller when a nonparametric component $f(\cdot)$ is added to the Fay-Herriot model; small areas can borrow more strength from the other areas. The coefficients of variation comparisons show that SP-SAE outperforms the Fay-Herriot model, and the Fay-Herriot model outperforms the direct estimators. In this research, we use SVR to estimate the regression function, but any other machine learning methods can be used as well in this framework.

Appendix

Nineteen predictors in the example: STATE is a categorical variable and all other 18 variables are quantitative from 2011-2015 ACS 5-year estimates.

- (1) POB: Proportion of black persons, 2011-2015
- (2) POH: Proportion of Hispanic persons, 2011-2015
- (3) PHS: Proportion of persons with high school + education, 2011-2015
- (4) PCE: Proportion of persons with college + education, 2011-2015
- (5) TAX: Property tax per capita, 2011-2015
- (6) STATE: 51 jurisdictions (categorical variable)
- (7) INCOME: Mean income per capita, 2011-2015
- (8) HouINCOME: Median Household income, 2011-2015
- (9) POVERTY: Proportion of persons experiencing poverty, 2011-2015
- (10) UNEMPLOY: Unemployment rate, 2011-2015
- (11) HouSIZE: Household size, 2011-2015
- (12) FEMALEH: Proportion of households with a female head-of-household, 2011-2015
- (13) CHILDREN: Proportion of households with children under 18 years of age, 2011-2015
- (14) ONEPERSON: Proportion of one-person households, 2011-2015
- (15) POPULATION: Population, 2011-2015
- (16) AGERATIO: Ratio of persons age 65+ to age 18+, 2011-2015
- (17) HOMEVALUE: Median home value, 2011-2015
- (18) COMMUTE30: Proportion of workers with commute time less than 30 minutes, 2011-2015
- (19) SECURITY: Social Security recipients, 2011-2015

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